

**The Effect of Interest Rates as an Instrument for Financial Repression on Nigeria's
Economic Growth**

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of interest rate on the economic growth of the Nigerian economy. The study determined the effect of interest rate on economic growth of Nigeria. The data for the study was obtained from the statistical bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria from 1986-2021. ARDL Technique was used for the analysis of data. It was found that Interest Rate and Broad Money Supply have a positive significant effect on GDP whereas, Inflation Rate was found to be negatively related to GDP. The study generally recommended that interest on loan funds should be repressed for investors to reinvest profits.

Keywords: Interest Rate, Financial Repression, Economic Growth, Inflation, ARDL
JEL index classification: G12, G23, F43, P24, C13

INTRODUCTION

The decline of oil prices in 1970s had a negative impact on economies that depended on it, including Nigeria. It also created numerous difficulties for other aspects of the economy, with disastrous effects even on commodity prices. This led to structural imbalances brought on by an economic downturn. Although the 1980s economic reforms saw some notable levels of development, particularly in the financial system, there were still a great deal of unresolved economic issues; in particular, interest rates have remained sky-high with disastrous effects on the borrowing rates and investment in Nigeria (Jelilov 2016). Interest rate is a very important factor in how monetary policy measures are transmitted to financial repression operations and its effect on economic growth.

Interest rate behavior has historically had a significant role in determining investment activity and, ultimately, economic growth of a nation. Economic growth is dependent on investment levels because investment depends on the interest rate associated with borrowing money from the market. Therefore, if the rate is high, investment will be low, and if the rate is low, investment will increase. Hence, there is a need to support an interest rate regime that will

ensure moderate investment costs, thereby boosting economic growth at a minimal cost to the economy. (Charles and Adeyeye 2021).

The idea or policy that a set of government rules, laws, and other non-market constraints prevents the financial intermediaries of an economy from operating at their full potentials are known as financial repression. Interest rate caps, liquidity ratio requirements, high bank reserve requirements, capital controls, exchange rates, limits on market access into the financial sector, credit ceilings, and restrictions on how credit is allocated are examples of policies that repress the financial system. (Gitau & Kosimbei, 2018).

Massive income and financial shortfalls have forced the Nigerian government to take on excessive domestic and foreign debt since the end of 2019 to cover its deficits. It is urgent for the government to consider strategies to manage its debts and the servicing accruing to such loans as government debts (both domestic and international) continue to soar at an alarming rate in an economy with a high inflation rate. Financial repression is one of the likely strategies the government will use to manage its domestic debt. (Jafarov *et al.*, 2019).

To achieve goals connected to lowering domestic debt loads and getting affordable loans for the government and businesses, the government may impose legal limits on interest rates, credit allocations by commercial banks and other financial institutions, and capital movements. It entails the government capping interest rates. These measures are typically use when shocks to an economy or the entire global economic system cause the government to incur significant domestic debt. (Mbugua 2020).

Several studies have been carried on financial repression and economic growth for instance Chan (2021), Edet (2021), Jahangir & Nirob (2020), Ebrahimian & Madanizadeh (2020), and Gitau & Kosimbei, (2018) stated that financial system is described as repressed when led to resource misallocation and inhibited economic growth, with interest rates historically heavily regulated before gradual liberalization. Interest rate controls are frequently identified as a primary repressive financial policy when intentionally maintained at low levels during the planned economy to encourage heavy industry development. Factors such as negative real interest rates, high taxation on financial returns, and reserve requirements contribute to Nigeria's authoritarian financial environment. The government sought strategies to prevent future recessions while promoting financial sector growth. Key financial sector reforms include interest rate liberalization, enhanced monetary policy, cessation of priority sector lending, improved central bank oversight,

bank regulation, debt recovery enhancement, and capital market expansion. These changes are expected to facilitate efficient financial resource allocation, fostering increased investment and capital formation.

Taking the case of Nigeria whereby its government have taken greatly the intervention of channeling funds for a priority sector, either crop and livestock agriculture, small and medium scale firms, housing scheme etc. One way that government financing expenditures apart from tax revenues is by forcing the private sector, pension funds, insurance companies, commercial banks and any other public financial institutions to engage them as captive audience in financial repression. This research focus on the assessment of the impact of interest rate as an instrument of financial repression on economic growth of Nigeria which is motivated by the recent fiscal challenges of government, which have significant effect on public finances.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A Brief Illustration of Interest Rate and Financial Repression Mechanism

Think of a market where there are three different categories of participants: depositors, borrowers, and financial institutions (banks). Due to market imperfections and other transaction costs, depositors do not deal with borrowers directly; instead, they deposit their savings in banks, which subsequently lend them to borrowers. Savers provide liquid assets that can be used by borrowers to finance investments. Borrowers must pay interest to financial institutions, and financial institutions must pay interest to savers. Financial institutions tolerate a positive gap between the interest rates they charge on loans to borrowers and the interest rates they pay on deposits to savers.

For the purposes of illustration, imagine there are no reserve requirements that the margin is exogenous, stable, and equal to zero, and that intermediaries simply act as middlemen by lending savers' money to borrowers. Without restrictions, the interest rate balances the supply of deposits with the loanable funds, bringing both the deposits and loans markets to equilibrium. There will be an excess supply for loans if the authorities instead set a legally binding administrative ceiling on the interest rate on loans (below the level of market clearing equilibrium). The lower rate will stimulate borrowers to enhance their demand for loans, but it will also encourage financial institutions to reduce their supply to remain profitable. Because the ceiling lowers interest rates and reduces the volume of loans compared to free-market equilibrium, it also lowers the

equilibrium volume and interest rates on deposits. As a result, they must reduce the interest paid on deposits, which will reduce the supply of deposits and thereby reduce the supply of money.

Given that the demand for loans is anticipated outpacing supply, how will intermediaries choose borrowers when interest rates are capped? In addition to increasing non-interest costs (like fees and commissions) to get around the restriction, intermediaries could be pickier about the quality of their loans by giving credit only to the least risky projects, giving preference to their current long-term clients (like maximizing long-term profits by rewarding loyalty), or making selections based on non-economic criteria (such as personal connections)

The distribution of credit is likely to be inefficient if borrowers are chosen based on these factors; even a selection that favors less risky borrowers may stifle innovation and restrict loan availability to potentially lucrative but risky ventures. This can be used as justification for direct government intervention in the choice of borrowers, such as mandating that intermediaries provide a minimum amount (or percentage) of loans to industries, endeavors, or borrowers' categories. As a result, it is likely that interest rate caps on loans will be combined with some forms of directed lending.

It should be noted that a loan interest rate ceiling could benefit certain borrowers at the expense of depositors who receive lower rates on their deposits, borrowers who would be able to borrow in a market equilibrium but are now excluded due to the rationing process, and depositors who withdraw from the market because of the lower rates. In all these situations, financial repression would be a type of quasi-fiscal operation where certain agents are effectively taxed (and others are taxed out of the market) to pay for the advancement of a public purpose.

Impact of Interest Rate on Economic Growth

In the past ten years, nations have implemented Negative Interest Rate Policies (NIRP) among other unorthodox monetary policy tools to combat low inflation and promote economic growth, Central Banks now charge interest on reserves kept in their possession by intermediaries rather than paying it. When market interest rates drop to low or even negative levels, intermediaries may need to reduce loan interest rates, but they are reluctant to reduce deposit rates by the same amount. This is especially true for retail depositors, as they understand that a negative deposit interest rate will prompt customers to withdraw their money and transfer it to other institutions that can guarantee them insurance and interest. (Iglesias-casal & Neto, 2021).

A severe fall in the real gross domestic product growth rate is required for the interest rate to begin oscillating at double-digit levels. This suggests that an economy's output performance is significantly influenced by interest rates (Inam and Etim 2020). In some circumstances, such as lowering interest rates is employed as an expansionary monetary policy, raising interest rates is necessary to reduce the rate of inflation. To some extent, developing nations like Nigeria might not be able to use this. Interest rate fluctuations produce significant market uncertainty that is particularly harmful to direct investment in the local economy.

Njie and Badjie (2021) examined that it is impossible to attain the goal of sustainable economic expansion because of unstable and rising interest rates. A high-interest rate environment is vital for the performance and returns of any given investment. Interest rate level is used to evaluate the impact of financial repression and liberalization on economic growth.

Charles and Adeyeye (2021) examined the effects of interest rates on domestic investments and economic growth in Nigeria. The Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach was used in the investigation. The model's findings showed that the Money Supply is considerable and has a favorable impact on interest rates. The study concluded that Nigeria's historically low investment levels are a result of the country's high and erratic interest rates on borrowing. Therefore, enhancing investment-friendly rates of interest through the creation and execution of financial policies is essential for fostering economic growth in Nigeria.

Dorothy *et al.* (2021) investigated the impact of few macroeconomic factors, such as interest rates and inflation, on Malaysia's economic development from 2010 to 2018. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach is used to estimate the variables' relationships with one another. In the long run, the inflation rate influences economic growth favorably, but the interest rate has the opposite effect.

Farouk *et al.* (2021), studied the impact of interest rate movement on Nigerian Economic Growth (EG). The study period of 1986 to 2018 using an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) was concluded that Interest Rate has a significant impact on Nigeria Economic Growth positively with a stable estimation.

Iglesias-casal and Neto (2021), Examined how negative interest rates affect bank profitability and risk-taking. Over the period 2011–2019, a sample of 2596 banks from European countries were used. The authors concluded that implementing negative interest rate policies reduces banks' net interest margin.

Inam and Etim (2020), investigated the effect of interest rate on economic growth in Nigeria spanning the period of 1970–2016. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) techniques were engaged to achieve the objectives. The study revealed that: there is a negative and significant relationship between regulated interest rate and economic growth in Nigeria; there is a negative and significant relationship between deregulated interest rate and economic growth in Nigeria; there is a negative and significant relationship between interest rate and economic growth in Nigeria. High interest rate is detrimental to economic growth in Nigeria.

Sultana (2020) investigated the impacts of money supply, inflation rate and interest rate on economic growth of Bangladesh from the period of 1981 to 2016. The study employed the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) model. The empirical analysis shows that broad money supply, inflation rate, interest rate possesses a long-run association with economic growth. Interest rate negatively related with the economic growth in the long run because of the deterioration of investment in the economy.

Hashim *et al.* (2019), investigated the dynamic relationship between selected macroeconomic variables, including unemployment, inflation, interest rate and economic growth, in Malaysia. Quarterly time series data from the first quarter of 2001 to the fourth quarter of 2017 was utilized. The Johansen Juselius Co-integration test and the Granger Causality test in Vector Error Correction framework were used to evaluate the relationships between the study variables. The findings suggested that a relationship exists between the variables.

Jelilov (2016), studied the impact of interest rate on economic growth by taking an example with Nigeria from 1990 to 2013. The result concluded using Ordinary Least Square method, that interest rate has a positive impact on growth; however, growth can be improved by lowering the interest rate, which will increase investment.

Keynesian Theory of Public Debt

Since it serves the interests of the whole public, Keynesians see fiscal policy as the best means of fostering economic growth. According to Keynes, when the government borrows money domestically to pay its expenses, it takes money out of private pockets that would otherwise be jobless; therefore, private consumers' consumption levels are unaffected. When the government reinvests these monies in the economy, the aggregate demand increases significantly, which boosts output and employment. Therefore, public domestic borrowing should be used to affect how well an economy performs. On the other hand, domestic borrowing reduces the amount of loanable

funds, which increases the rate of interest. Domestic borrowing has an impact on growth via this transmission mechanism (Okwu *et al.* 2016). A higher interest rate will discourage private investment if interest rates affect investment and the connection between the two is negative. The partial crowding out of deficit funding has been used to describe this decline in private investment. It is only partially effective because less private investment is being crowded out because of government debt issuance. Aggregate demand, output, and employment all decline because of the decline in private investment.

Keynesian theory for public debt states that increasing public debt does not increase interest rates so long as policy can successfully manage the psychology of the debt market (Hengjie, Murray & Ali, 2021). Keynes argued that increased government spending through taxes and loans positively affects the economy since it increases capital.

METHODOLOGY

Nature and Source of Data Collection

This study adopted secondary data, which covers 35-year period (1986-2021). There will be engagement of annual time series data for the analysis and will be obtain from the Central Bank of Nigeria Bulletin 2022.

The Specification of Model

The study adopted Sultana, (2020) model which was well modified and structured to suit the variables under which the OLS main assumption is that the errors must be uncorrelated.

$$y_t = \alpha + \beta tXt + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots$$

$$RGDP_t = f (INR_t, INF_t, BMS_t)$$

Whereby:

RGDP_t Real Gross Domestic Product

INR_t Interest Rate

INF Inflation

BMS Broad Money Supply

The equation is present in econometric form as:

$$RGDP_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 INR_t + \alpha_2 INF_t + \alpha_3 BMS_t + v_t$$

Estimation Technique

To achieve the aimed objective of the study, annual time series data of the variables is used. The estimation technique employed is the Ordinary Least Square Technique.

Unit Root Test

For checking of Unit Root, Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) test is engaged on the regression, which is specify in the equation below:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma Y_{t-1} + \delta_1 \Delta Y_{t-1} + \dots + \delta_{p-1} \Delta Y_{t-p+1} + \varepsilon_t$$

$$\Delta RGDP_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma RGDP_{t-1} \sum_{1=i}^m \delta_1 \Delta RGDP_{t-1} \dots + \varepsilon_t$$

$$\Delta INR_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma INR_{t-1} \sum_{1=i}^m \delta_1 \Delta INR_{t-1} \dots + \varepsilon_t$$

$$\Delta INF_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma INF_{t-1} \sum_{1=i}^m \delta_1 \Delta INF_{t-1} \dots + \varepsilon_t$$

$$\Delta BMS_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma BMS_{t-1} \sum_{1=i}^m \delta_1 \Delta BMS \dots + \varepsilon_t$$

The Auto-Regressive Distributed Lagged Bounds Tests for Co-integration

To analyze the long-run and short run dynamics relationship interactions among the variables of interest (Real Gross Domestic Product, Deposit Interest Rate, Broad Money Supply and Inflation), the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) co-integration technique is applied and specified as:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 Y_{t-1} + \beta_2 X_{1t-1} + \beta_2 X_{2t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_{1i} \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_{2i} \Delta X_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_{3i} \Delta X_{2t-i} + \varepsilon_t$$

Diagnostic and Stability Tests

To ensure the estimations obtained are robust and reliable, a series of diagnostic and reliability tests is conducted by examining functional form correctness of serial correlation and heteroscedasticity using the Lagrange multiplier test and the regression of squared residuals on squared fitted values respectively-CUSUM and the CUSUMSQ.

DISCUSSIONS

Unit Root Test

This study conducted the unit root test to ascertain the stationarity level of each variable in the series, which is one of the preconditions for ARDL technique. Therefore, result in table 1 shows that all the series are of level I (0) or of I (1). Hence, it proves the suitability of ARDL technique.

Table 1: Augmented-Dickey Fuller Unit Root Test at 5% critical value

VARIABLE	ADF at 5%		Both Trend and Intercept		Critical Value at 5%	
	LEVEL		1 ST ORDER	LEVEL	1 st ORDER	ORDER OF COINTEG.
GDP	1.9007 (1.0000)		-4.3056 (0.0095)	-3.5628	-3.5628	I (1)
INR	-3.6167 (0.0428)		----- -----	-3.5442	-----	I (0)
INF	-3.1876 (0.1087)		-6.1600 (0.0002)	-3.5950	-3.6121	I (1)
BMS	-3.3778 (0.0189)		----- -----	-2.9511	-----	I (0)

Source: Researcher’s computation using E-views 9.0, 2022

Co-integration Test

This test was conducted using bound test techniques to determine whether the variables of the model have converged in the long run or not. The test used 5% critical value in taking decision about the cointegration in the long run. The result presented in **Table 2** shows the F-statistics values of 4.619567 that is greater than the upper and lower bounds values at 5% level of significance. That indicates the existence of long-run cointegration relationship among the variables in the model.

Table 2: Summary of Co-integration (Bounds Result)

Statistics	Significance	Critical value Bounds		Decision
		I (0) Bounds	I (1) Bounds	
	10%	2.97	3.74	
F-stat. 4.619567	5%	3.38	4.23	Co-integration exist
	2.5%	3.8	4.68	
	1%	4.3	5.23	

Source: Researcher’s computation using E-views 9.0, 2022

Selected ARDL Estimation Model

The establishment of cointegration among the variables makes the estimation of the ARDL bound test model to present together with the diagnostic test in order to ascertain the level of the effect of the explanatory variables on the explained variable. Hence, **Table 3** shows the selected ARDL based on Akaike Information Criterion

Table 3: Selected ARDL (4, 4, 0, 0) Estimation Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
GDP _{t-1}	1.239551	0.188854	6.563545	0.0000
GDP _{t-2}	-0.191490	0.302308	-0.633427	0.5349
GDP _{t-3}	-0.548795	0.296552	-1.850590	0.0817
GDP _{t-4}	0.553543	0.208526	2.654554	0.0167
INR	7.17E+10	2.23E+11	0.321111	0.7520
INR _{t-1}	1.06E+11	2.45E+11	0.432602	0.6707
INR _{t-2}	-5.64E+11	2.49E+11	-2.262889	0.0370
INR _{t-3}	2.97E+11	2.46E+11	1.209665	0.2430
INR _{t-4}	-4.69E+11	2.18E+11	-2.147894	0.0464
INF	3.25E+10	2.55E+10	1.274011	0.2198
BMS	-3.76E+11	3.96E+11	-0.949881	0.3555
@TREND	4.76E+25	1.58E+11	3.005855	0.0080
COINTEGRATION EQUATION (-1)	-0.855763	0.010677	5.222902	0.0001

Adjusted R-squared=0.998635

D-Watson Stat. = 2.500337

Source: Researcher's computation using E-views 9.0, 2022

The result from **Table 3** confirmed the fitness of the model by the adjusted R-square value of 99% and Durbin-Watson Statistics of 2.5 that approaches to and not far away from no autocorrelation. Hence, the lagged variables are significant, proving the fitness of the model.

Table 4: ARDL Cointegration and Long Run Form, Selected Model (4, 4, 0, 0)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
INR	1.9000	8.73000	1.229211	0.2357
INF	-1.37413	5.76675	-1.039750	0.3130
BMS	7.1900	7.05000	0.988084	0.3370
@TREND	-0.855763	0.01067	-1.390444	0.0001

Source: Researcher's computation using E-views 9.0, 2022

Diagnostic Tests

ARDL bound test is valid on the normality of the distributed error terms that are serially correlated and homoscedastic on the stability of the coefficient over time. Therefore, CUSUM and CUSUMSQ are conducted, and results are accepted which are shown in the figure below and the model is stable since the statistics lie within 5% critical bound.

Figure: I

Discussions and Findings

Table 4 shows the long run interaction of the variables together with their error corrections term or speed of the adjustment and is negative (-0.855763), less than one and significant (0.0001) confirming the stability of the model and the presence of the long run relationship. This means that whenever there is a divergence of the equilibrium from the path in the short run, about 85% of the disequilibrium can be restore to the long run path. However, the coefficient of interest rates shows a positive effect on economic growth, suggesting that a unit increase in interest rates will inflow positively on economic growth to (1.9000) in the long run. Hence, this finding is in line with Njie and Badjie (2021) and Farouk *et al.* (2021). The coefficient of Broad Money Supply have a

positive (7.1900) and insignificance long run relationships with economic growth which goes in line with Charles and Adeyeye (2021) study while inflation rate has a negative (-1.37413) and insignificance long run relation with economic growth.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the findings in this study, it is recommended that the government of Nigeria should prudently manage the country's interest rate policy by repressing the cost in borrowing for investors to reinvest profits instead of using it for high repayment. In other form, interest rate can be without repression on savings because it attracts incentives to save rather than spend, which avails loanable funds and geared economic growth.

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